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Editorial

The Editorial Board is pleased to bring out the Volume Two & Issue Two of 'GENIUS', An Interdisciplinary Half Yearly Research Journal. Recently, all over the world number of economic and managerial changes are being taken place. To tackle the problems of business and to remove the bottlenecks of enterprises, the well thought and all embarrassing articles need to be published for the businessmen, academicians, investors, etc. The global economic situation is not much favorable for the socio-economic development of Indian economy. In this situation, the sustained efforts with honest management skills will be of much helpful. The **Genius**, newly established yearly journal is trying to reach the readers of all sections of society. The authors have covered different aspects and they have helped to make this issue in a more comfortable & readable. The articles included in this journal covers from all India level. The publisher will be happy if the readers bring their suggestions for the further improvement of this newly started journal.

Assit. Prof. Vinay S. Hatole

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‘जिनिअस’ या सहामयि प्रसिध्द झालेली मते मुख्य संपादक, संपादक मंडळ व सल्लागार मंडळास मान्य असतीलच असे नाही. या नियतकालिकात प्रसिध्द करण्यात आलेली लेखकाची मते ही त्याची वैयक्तिक मते आहेत. तसेच शोधनिबंधाची जबाबदारी स्वतः लेखकावर राहिल.

हे नियतकालिक मालक, मुद्रक, प्रकाशक विनय शंकरराव हातोले यांनी अजिंठा कॉम्प्युटर अँड प्रिंटर्स, जयसिंगपूरा, विद्यापीठ गेट, औरंगाबाद येथे मुद्रित व प्रकाशित केले.

A Study of the Parents 'Attitude Towards Girls' Education at Primary Level in Slum Area in Aurangabad- City

Dr. Muntajeeb Ali Baig

Assistant Professor, Marathwada College of Education, Aurangabad.

Introduction

“If you educate a boy, you educate an individual but if you educate a girl, you educate a family”. Low participation of female students in primary education by Teshomenekatibeb, May2002. “The educational background of parents, for most of the mother plays a key role for more successful biographies of children”, Household structures, personal assets and socio-cultural aspects as determinants of school dropout rates; Case from urban slums in Ahmedabad, India, Master`s thesis, Sophia Volksen. If you look at above quotation you come to know how girls` education is important.

India is a developing country. After independence we have been striving for development in every section and sphere of life. Education is one of the most essential and fundamental needs of society.

Primary education is the foundation of the educational pattern but unfortunately through government so many facilities like breakfast, mid-day meal, free and compulsory education for all and other things given to students but primary education seems to have ample difficulties. In the undeveloped & back word areas of our country primary education requires efforts in order to increase the quantitative development. In this dissertation researcher intend to study some of the basic problems of primary education of girls in a slum area.

Statement of problem

A study of the parents` attitude towards girls` education at primary level in slum area in Aurangabad-city.

Operational Definitions

Aurangabad City

One of Taluka place city in Aurangabad district, known for the city of Gates.

Primary Level

It means from standard 1st to 8th.

Slum Area

Slum area means the low socio economic areas of Aurangabad city, where the people from different stratas live.

Assumption

- 1) Majority of the parents are financially weak.
- 2) Most of the parents are illiterate.

Objectives of Research

- 1) To find out the causes of poor enrollment of girls from slum area to Schools.
- 2) To find out the illiteracy rate of parents.
- 3) To find out the attitudes of parents towards girls education.
- 4) To find out the problems of parents in sending the girls to the Schools.

Hypothesis

- 1) The parents' attitude towards girl's education in slum areas is not positive.
- 2) The literacy rate of parents is responsible for it.
- 3) The financial condition of parents is also responsible for it.

Review of Past Research and Related Literature**Women Education in India**

Women constitute almost half of the population in the world. But the hegemonic masculine ideology made them suffer a lot as they were denied equal opportunities in different parts of the world. The rise of feminist ideas has, however, led to the tremendous improvement of women's condition throughout the world in recent times. Access to education has been one of the most pressing demands of these women's rights movements. Women education in India has also been a major preoccupation of both the government and civil society as educated women can play a very important role in the development of the country.

History of women education in India

Although in the Vedic period women had access to education in India, they had gradually lost this right. However, in the British period there was revival of interest in women's education in India. During this period, various socio-religious movements led by eminent persons like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidya Sagar emphasized on women's education in India. Mahatma Jyotiba Phule, Periyar and Babasaheb Ambedkar were leaders of the lower castes in India. However, women's education got a fillip after the country got independence in 1947 and the government has taken various measures to provide education to all Indian women. As a result, women's literacy rate has grown over the three decades and the growth of female literacy has in fact been higher than that of male literacy rate. While in 1971 only 20% of Indian women were literate, by the end of 2001, 54.16% female were literate. The growth of female literacy rate is 14.87% as compared to 11.72% of that male literacy rate.

Importance of women education in India

Women education in India plays a very important role in the overall development of the country. It not only helps in the development of half of the human resources, but in improving the quality of life at home and outside. Educated women not only tend to promote education to their girls children, but also can provide letter guidance to all their children. Moreover educated women can also help in the reduction of infant mortality rate and growth of the population.

<http://www.indiaedu.com/education-india/women-edu.html>

Women's education important for health

Patil (2010-11-13), New, Delhi 13 (IANS) president Pratibha Patil Saturday termed women's education as the determinant for good health of women and children.

Education is a powerful driver of health. The relationship between poverty, lack of education and limited access to health service, is well recognized, patil said, inaugurating a two day international conference on 'Partnership for maternal, new born and child health's here.

India has recently enacted a Right to Education Act under which all children in the age group of 6-14. Will receive free education. When fully realized, this will have a profound impact on health indicators. As well, the president said.

Educated women tend to provide better guidance to their children and also promote education of girl children she said.

<http://www.sify.com/news/women's-education-important-for-health-patil-news-health-klrja.html>

Women's Education in India: a Critical Analysis Verma Yoginder S., (Oct 9, 2009) Institute of Management studies, Himachal Pradesh, University, Shimla, India In India, women education particularly at higher education needs special attention. Girl has less access to quality education. Even in the professional course, the number of girls is less a compared to boys. The girls from backward communities face several discrimination Despite reservation quota, they never got opportunity to enter a college whatever is the course of study latest data show that about one is 17 Muslim girls, one in 10 Hindu girls, one in six Sikh girls and one in six Christian girls, and avail higher education. Scheduled caste/ scheduled tribes and other backward class girls have poorer access to higher education than higher-caste girls.

<http://www.indiaedu.com/critical.analysis>

Research Design and Methodology

Meaning of Research Design

The terms Research consists of two words, Re + Search. 'Re' means again and again. 'Search' means to find out it is the process by which a person observes the phenomenon again and again and collects the data. The data may be both numerical and of non-numerical values.

Def: (Moule George. J.) “Research is the systematic objective and accurate search for the solution to well defined problems.”

Methodology of Research

Research methods are of utmost importance in a research process. They describe the various steps of the plan of attack to be adopted in solving a research problem. Such as a manner in which problems are formulated, the definition of terms the choice of subjects for investigation, analysis and inter-relation of data and the processes of inferences and generalization.

Types of Normative Survey Research

Survey studies are conducted to collect detailed description of existing phenomena with the intent of employing data to justify current conditions and practices or to make more intelligent plans for improving them. Survey may be narrow or broad in scope surveys may be narrow or broad in scope. Some surveys encompass several countries, states or regions, or they may be limited to one country, state or region. Survey studies describe and specify the properties of educational phenomena.

School surveys

According to good (1966) the comprehensive school survey usually covers the following aspects of the school system, aim, outcomes, pupil achievement, curriculum, method and instructional aides, etc.

School surveys may be conducted at the local, state, regional or national level or they may be undertaken at various levels of instruction. Elementary, secondary or higher.

Researcher has used survey method to understand the attitude look to the problems of the girl’s education, to find out the information about the facilities in school.

Causal Comparative Research

This provides a method of investigation to study variables as they occur in a natural setting, because they have already occurred or are not manipulable.

Experimental Research

Which provides a method of investigation to derive basic relationships among phenomena under controlled conditions or more simply, to identify the conditions underlying the occurrence of a given phenomenon.

Tools of Research

Any Researcher requires various data gathering tools, which facilitate original research investigations and observations leading to useful and valuable results.

Data collection is essentially an important part of research process. Researchers generally attempt to gather evidences either for verifying new hypothesis or for checking current conclusions. To accomplish their objectives researchers obtain dates from documentary or field sources.

Tools of research

- 1) Questionnaire
- 2) Observations
- 3) Interview
- 4) Psychological tests
- 5) Inventories
- 6) Opinionative
- 7) E tools
- 8) Rating scale
- 9) Check list
- 10) Aptitude test
- 11) Nominating technique

By above tools researcher has chosen questionnaire tool for collecting data.

Tool used for collecting data**Recommendations**

Recommendations for the parents:-

- 1) As most of the parents think that education is necessary then they also have to understand the education is necessary for girls also.
- 2) As most of the parent's economic condition is very low then they have to send their child in Z.P. school as there is free education for the students and also lunch is given by the government.
- 3) In Aurangabad there is the facility of separate schools for girls then if the parents are not interested to send their daughters to school because of co-education school then they have to send their daughters to the girl's school.
- 4) As most of the parents told to understand the importance of education should be properly guided to encourage sending their girls to school.

Recommendations for school

- 1) The school authority should provide all the possible facilities for the purpose of girl education.
- 2) The teacher in school may be asked to go very close to girls and their personal difficulties'.
- 3) Publicity programmers:- It should be stretched in from of preparing and presenting commentaries and films worsening women's education
- 4) Part time training and employment of women: - As there is a shortage of women teacher a scheme of part time employment of women teachers should be launched.

Recommendation for Government

1) Improvements programme

Like construction of quarters for women teachers' rural allowances for women teachers' construction of girls hostel should be started on large scale.

2) Seminars on women education

Seminars on women's education should be held frequently in different regions and in state in order to cause moments in the off-air of agencies.

3) Continuation of classes

Continuation of classes may be started in the existing schools for those who have left the school for those who have left the schools and are not in position to join during day time due to various social and economic reasons.

4) Facilities in backward areas

Facilities in backward areas should be provided to girl students in the form of free residential accommodation and special allowances to woman teacher.

5) Technical institute for girls

It should be started and governments should give maximum possible facilities in this regard.

Conclusions

- 1) Majority of the parents of the slum area are literate.
- 2) The occupation of major of the parent is labour.
- 3) The total number of girls in the area are 192 in which 33% girls are going to primary school and remaining are not going to school whose age are school going age.
- 4) Because of economic condition parents do not show their interest for sending their daughters to school.
- 5) Majority of the parents think the education is necessary.
- 6) Labour is the earning business of majority, parents so that their monthly income is very low.
- 7) There are few schools in locality.
- 8) There is facility of separate schools for girls in the Aurangabad city.
- 9) There is no part time school for girls who are working for earning the bread.
- 10) The parent's attitude is not towards mixed school.
- 11) The girls thinking (78 %) about education is positive they think that education is necessary.
- 12) Majority of the families had 4-6 members of group of family.
- 13) Majority of the families had 1-2 girls in the family.
- 14) The majority of families were having 3 earning members in the family.

- 15) Majority of the families were having their income below 2000 per month.
- 16) Majority of the respondent were not in fevour of Mixed School.
- 17) Majority of the houses were away from school.

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